

Coevolutionary network analysis of teaching core strictu sensu: an exploratory study of the management area in Brazil

1 INTRODUCTION

Since its reformulation in the late 1990s, when the area of management was primary concerned with becoming interdisciplinary, until the 2010s the concern focused on relevance, internationalization, and perhaps social impact (Mascarenhas, Zambaldi and Moraes, 2011; Bertero, Vasconcelos, et al. 2013; Wood Jr, Costa, Lima, & Guimarães, 2016; Mendonça Neto, Vieira, & Oyadomari, 2019; Wood-Jr & Souza, 2019). The community has grown in number, and to reconcile such growth with continued regulatory pressure for quality, productivity, competition for grants, the community has delivered answers that are unstudied. The teaching relations among teaching core at strictu sensu departments (from now on called PPGs) is a response of the community without studies in the academic literature in Brazil.

The origin of organizations and institutions is the classic concern of institutional theory. A critical challenge, then, is to explain the genesis of organizations and institutions, and particularly why and how specific elements combine to make new organizational arrangements possible at a certain point of time and space (Powell, Packalen, & Whittington, 2012). Padget and Powell (2012) coevolutionary theory of social networks establishes the link between the emergence of an organizational novelty and the relational trajectory of the system with its consequences and/or ruptures. Its assumption is institutional novelties will imply transformations in the relational arrangement of/among organizations/domains, and such novelties can be revealed by constitutive ties. Thus, to identify such constitutive structure, there are two research strategies. First, knowing the new structure, it is feasible to map relationally adjacent domains with the purpose of identifying isomorphic transpositions. This is a strategy that favors a cross-cutting approach. Another approach, the one adopted in this study, is to perform a longitudinal approach in the studied domain, following the evolution of trails formed among organizations, to eventually identify novelties in the constitution of new relational arrangements and their possible relationships with new sociotechnical capacities. By sociotechnical capacity, the reader must understand social contributive technologies that enable the coordination of activities in space and time. As an example, management and communication technologies, which in the human context allow multiple spaces in a neighborhood (Ujwary-Gil, 2020). Therefore, production is viable, not only in person but also in virtual spaces.

For a feasible study, it is necessary a time variable network analysis, only in this way it is possible to detect the constitution of new forms of organizations and then have access to the genesis of institutions and organizations (Padget and Powell, 2012). It is a temporal network analysis, within a domain of skills and competencies, sensitive to transformations. In the case described here, it is the strictu sensu system, in the domain of teaching skills. Thus, the research question is how does the evolution of networks among teaching cores in the areas of management, and regulatory acts, reveal the constitution of organizational novelties in strictu sensu programs in Brazil? To answer this question, it is necessary to answer two secondary questions: 1 – What does the organizational genesis of the system tell us about its directions; and 2 – How the structure reacts to the emergence of organizational novelties in the system. Therefore, our secondary objectives are 1 – Construction of the longitudinal digraph for extraction of longitudinal metrics that subsidizes (i) Extraction, on an annual basis, of the rate of strongly connected components, or cyclic integrality, and (ii) Annual test of the plausibility of probabilistic distributions of the power law (the logic of preferential connection) and exponential (the logic of homogeneity in connections) to have access to deviations on both probabilistic models; and 2 – mapping of the relevant ordinances and resolutions from Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) and Ministry of Education (MEC) to have access to the system's reactions to organizational novelties.

For the constitution of the empirical model, this study was considered CAPES documentary data from the years 1990 to 2020 for the context of strictu sensu programs in the areas of Brazilian management - Administration and Engineering III. That is, from the decade of its main restructuring to the present day. We will, in addition to structurally characterizing the network formed by such shares, counteract the genesis of networks formed between PPGs with regulatory acts of CAPES and MEC to find an answer to the research question.

2 THEORETICAL MODEL

2.1 Coevolutionary theory of social networks

The coevolutionary theory of social networks is based on a proposal of exaptation, that is, the translation of solutions and theories among different areas of knowledge. Here the hypercyclical theory of autocatalysis applies to the genesis of social networks. How? Padgett and Powell (2012) note that since the last century, an organization has never been defined beyond the postulate: competition between companies generates pressure for ideal policies and practices. This postulate does not define an organization, it only explains that in the aggregate of organizations, competition among the best defines the practices of the field. There have been advances, as in the theory of transaction costs (Coase, 1937; Williamson, 1973 as quoted in Padgett, 1997, p. 199) and principal-agent (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Fama, 1980 as cited in Padgett, 1997, p. 199), but such advances only evidenced the company as a set of contracts. However, Padgett and Powell (2012) suggest that the steady flow of people through organizations defines an organization. Thus, the authors propose, in analogy to the hypercycle process of chemicals, that organizations are the synthesis of the individuals who constitute them, a model of networks that capture their dynamics can define organizations and put in evidence systemic changes.

Autocatalysis systems are chemical energy dissipation systems with self-reproduction criteria (Padgett & Powell, 2012). In chemistry, the breeding criterion is defined by Moore's neighborhood rule, which states that there is a probability that $\frac{1}{8}$ of the molecules in a neighborhood react to each other, and that the byproduct of the initial reaction triggers new reactions with neighboring molecules. In the chemical process, the goal is transformation, chemical elements react to each other and transform. Therefore, in a compound where there are several reagents in a non-homogeneous state, the process of chemical catalysis will occur differently in time and space. The interesting thing is that the reagents when transforming generate by-products of the reaction, eventually, these by-products feed other reactions, producing a continuous cycle of reactions until the different saturations of reagents in the environment reach saturation. These successive reactions may end up reencountering the reaction that initiated the whole process by initiating a new reagent sequence. When that happens, we have what we call an autocatalysis hypercycle.

The translation of chemistry into economic sociology proposed by Padgett and Powell (2012) is exactly in the understanding that the key point to explaining a company is its skills and competencies. The skills and competencies necessary for the economic production process to be carried out are the meeting point between an individual/company and a chemical/compound reagent. Chemical reactions are the result of a natural tendency of the elements to compart the electron octet and therefore stabilize. The bond between molecules is a way to make up for molecular stability. In organizations, the composition between individuals and companies follows the same logic when it comes to the search for stability, and social bonds are the equivalent of electron exchange in hypercycle chemistry. Therefore, the central point lies in the skills of individuals or organizations. Particularly in the asymmetry of capabilities among individuals and organizations, which generates instability for the skill set necessary for the operation. In a chemical hypercycle, where the predisposition to react chemically is an implicit nature among reagents, in addition to producing stability to reagents, there is also the production of by-products and the dissipation of energy. The chemical by-product of the

reaction, which is a new molecule, also seeks to establish new reactions with reagent molecules that had not yet been activated initiating new processes, and thus new cycles begin. In economic production, there is an organization where its employees are organized in such a way that there are reproductions and transformations that, once passed, promote other productions and transformations, continuously until the production cycle meets its beginning and restarts.

In the coevolutionary theory of social networks, an organization is formed by a non-random set of skills. And, to make up this set, in addition to the strategy of skills verticalization, another strategy is skills horizontalization, which and when integrate can form production and feedback cycles (Padgett, 1997). Padgett and Powell (2012) explain how coevolutionary theory uses an analogy with chemistry for the microsocial definition of an organization and can be a reference for the meso-social constitution of an industry or sector (Ramström, 2018). All this from the aggregate skills of individuals and/or organizations, besides being strongly inspiring to explain the production processes and the existing and emerging forms of production organization – lines, chains, associations, consortia, and networks. The authors also clarify that both an individual and a company have more skills than a chemical element. Therefore, $n+1$ cycles can pass through a production unit. In addition, and as an example, among many others, management, and communication technologies, in the human context, allow multiple spaces in the neighborhood. Therefore, production ties are viable in virtual spaces, such as distance learning, or even in meta-relational spaces, such as administrative boards, or in governance units (Fligstein & McAdam, 2012), such as CAPES's evaluation system. Through meta-relationships, we understand to be a sociotechnical system whose purpose is more coordinated than operational, and its by-product will have its characteristics. Evaluation/management boards are also subject to non-social relations, in addition to social relations. For example, in times when technological transitions represent a break with traditional technologies, non-social networks, as pressures for innovations underlying new socio-technical capabilities arise among technological innovations that also generate pressure on evaluation/management boards (Ujwary-Gil, 2020).

An autocatalysis hypercycle is a dynamic process and therefore, in addition to considering individual skills as a source of cross-cutting interactions between individuals, individuals/organizations, organizations/organizations, /organizations/regulatory agencies, individual skills are also a source of longitudinal relationships. But despite describing various forms of relationships inspired by reactions of autocatalysis, matrix algebra passes away from this proposition. The constitution of a tie is an important debate, but also little explored in networks.

2.2 Mechanisms of organizational genesis

Autocatalysis processes per se do not produce new forms of organization, the source of organizational novelties are constitutive cycles among $n + 1$ network domains (Padgett and Powell, 2012, p.11). Here the keyword for understanding an organizational novelty is a transposition. The transposition of a model among different domains triggers what Padgett and Powell (2012) call unfolding or networks rupture. It is expected that structurally the relational space will present changes in its structural setup.

The authors indicate at least eight mechanisms that would produce networks to unfold or rupture. All models start with the transposition mechanism, however, the way they are conducted in the target domain reflects their structure and how susceptible the target domain is predisposed to a gradual or disruptive embedding. By briefly describing each of the mechanisms it is possible to qualify them if they tend to be evolutionist or disruptive, the first is the transposition of an organizational novelty and its refunctionality as a structure response in the target domain. In this mechanism, the target structure processes the embedding according to its local assumptions. The second is anchoring to an existing model in an adjacent domain, but the target structure incorporates its specificities while maintaining the link with the adjacent

domain. The third is the incorporation of an organizational novelty but decoupled from the source domain, especially from the origin's organizational assumptions. The fourth is the migration of a model by homology, usually associated with the incorporation of different skills and competencies from those of the target domain. The fifth model is to dodge the conflict that can be established in the target domain and incorporate organizational novelty leading to a process of destination domain cleavage. The sixth model is disruptive, it is about purging the dissonant model of organizational novelty through community mobilization. The seventh model is the privatization of the destination domain, it is a disruptive model by transferring the domain to an environment of economic relations. Of course, the organizational novelty will come from the business group rationale. The eighth and final mechanism is the robust action of a powerful intermediary who orchestrates the vocalicity of different factions supporting multiple identities, even if in a contradictory way without truly assuming one of them, thus maintaining the different subdued factions and feeding dissensions.

2.3 Digraph theory

To make a matrix algebra adherent to dynamic analysis, our proposal is the contribution of the theory of digraphs in the structure and constitution of ties (Bang-Jensen & Gutin, 2007). A digraph is a directional graph and offers a network analysis algebra originated from the dilemma of the traveling salesman. This problem asks the following question: Given a list of cities and distances between each pair of cities, what is the shortest possible path that allows you to visit each city exactly once, then return to the city of origin? That is, retaking a path that has already been trodden represents inefficiency. Thus, to better represent the theory of coevolution proposed by Padget and Powell (2012), we will address the problem of directional relations.

A digraph D is formed by directional relationships in a finite set of vertices. A directional relationship is a relationship with the origin at a vertex i and destination in a vertex j (Bang-Jensen & Gutin, 2007). Some aspects are important to highlight. The first is the criterion for identifying isomorphic structures – which have the same shape. In graph algebra, the relationship $i - j$ is equal to $j - i$, if and only if the relationship between i and j is symmetrical and therefore isomorphic. In the algebra of the digraphs, there is no equality between $i \rightarrow j$ and $j \rightarrow i$. The direction of the relationship makes them asymmetric and therefore non-isomorphic. Symmetry in relationships is something that does not exist in nature, and because we are describing an empirical space it is necessary that even if reciprocal ties occur as in this case $i \rightarrow j$ and $j \rightarrow i$, the reciprocity imposed by the symmetry will not offer analytical distortions. In addition, in a directional relational space, it is possible to provide both symmetric and asymmetric structural metrics, which enables us to a wider range of analytical resources.

Strongly Connected Components – SCC (Bang-Jensen & Gutin, 2007) are clics composed of cycles formed among vertices. In a relational space of affiliations, if the matrix algebra of the graphs is adopted, and consequently the assumption that all relationships are symmetrical, what is adopted in the conversion of matrices from 2-mode to 1-mode is the mathematical criterion of projection, which is the matrix G product of a 2-mode – actor versus event, $a \times e$ – for its transposed G' . The effect of this mathematical maneuver, whether one wants the relations between actors $G X G'$ – or events $G' X G$ – is the 1-mode matrix constitution with symmetrical 1-mode relationships formed between actors and 1-mode formed between events (Wasserman and Faust, 2008). This characteristic is undesirable in the theory of coevolution of social networks.

In Moore's space of the theory of coevolution of social networks (Padget & Powell, 2012), which is the relational space of the theory of digraphs (Bang-Jensen & Gutin, 2007), we will have vertices that do not find components, so in a relational space G , it is necessary that the constitution of relationships capture the trail carried out by actors among different events.

2.3.1 Actors and their tracks

In the theory of the digraph, the Dilemma of the traveling salesman is enunciated as a problem of optimal trails. Therefore, the trajectory of the actors (Padgett, 2018; Padgett, Prajda, Rohr, & Schoots, 2020; Schoots, Rohr, Prajd, & Padgett, 2020) is the main attribute for the constitution of a relationship and therefore of a trail. Thus, a relationship of affiliation should not be seen as a problem of mathematical projection, but rather as the by-product of an ideal path among two or more vertices. The logic is that if actors co-occur in events, they may not be connecting all events, but rather composing a track that connects them. One of the problems of path constitutions is how to find paths that actors travel between events to form a digraph (Bang-Jensen & Gutin, 2007, pp. 95-170).

With a simplified notation, a digraph can be described as $D = (V, A, l, u, c)$, that is, a digraph is a set of vertices V , ties A , classification categories of V or A (l - lower limit, and $-u$ capacity) and costs c of V or A - the weight of loops or vertices that can be considered as a hierarchy. Although, it is possible the occurrence of complex relational spaces, that is, the occurrence of parallel ties. Thus, to establish a track it is feasible to establish a ranking for vertices or ties (V or A). In this study, we adopted to elaborate a ranking among events. Thus, a track A of actors a can be esteemed hierarchically from a ranking of non-repeated events as in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Translation from an affiliation record to a track according to a ranking u_t .

Note: The actor's track defined here by the ability of each vertex, expressed here by reflective ties. The hierarchical order is given in order from smallest to largest. Source: Prepared by the authors via Gephi (Bastian, Heymann and Jacomy, 2014).

This approach does not imply that clicks do not occur. If there is a population, or a sample with relational space representative of the population the clicks can be composed by the union of actor's tracks.

2.4 Genesis of networks

Two empirical approaches to analyze the genesis of networks were adopted in this text. The first is the rate of hypercycle formation given by the identification of Hamiltonian cycles by Robert Tarjan's in-depth research algorithm (1972 cited in Bang-Jensen & Gutin, 2007, p. 179-182). The second is the empirical analysis of the power-law distribution of Closet, Shalize and Newman, (2009) through the R library called Gillespie powerLaw (2015).

2.4.1 In-depth Search

To research cycles, the algorithm elaborated by Tarjan (1972, as quoted in Bang-Jensen & Gutin, 2007, p. 179-182) tries to build the cycle starting from a vertex and performing an in-depth search of the paths until being able to return to the starting point. When a cycle is found, the cycle vertices are grouped into vertices that form a track that returns to the starting point. Each cycle found is grouped as an SCC and the process is repeated until all cycles of a component are identified, totalized, and vertices are classified into strongly connected component groups. Vertices that are isolated, are exclusively enders or cycle initiators are classified as strong by themselves. It is a special case of an SCC that permits us to identify nodes who believe in skill verticalization. Tarjan's algorithm (1972, as cited in Bang-Jensen & Gutin, 2007, p. 179-182) was run each year via UCINET (Borgatti, Everett, & Freeman, 2002). UCINET calculates the rate of Strongly Connected Components (CR), which is a measure of

cyclic integrality of relational space. Its equation is $CR = \frac{(\#CFC-1)}{(N-1)}$ where N is the total number of vertices and $\#CFC$ is the total number of strongly connected components, the CR is 1 when there are no SCCs, and CR is 0 when all are in a single SCC and all relational space is represented by it (Borgatti, Everett, & Freeman, 2002). In this work, we are presenting $CR^* = 1 - CR$ to invert order. The occurrence indicates the moment from which relational space begins to contain Hamiltonian cycles or strongly connected components.

2.4.2 Power law

In this section, we mainly follow Closet, Shalizi & Newman (2009). A predominant number of statistical phenomena present empirical amounts that are grouped around a typical or average value. However, some phenomena have demonstrated a distinct behavior, not grouped around typical or average values. Among the phenomena, the nodal centrality k_i in networks can be highlighted. For an analysis of the behavior of networks regarding their relational constitution, the approach considered is probabilistic. Mathematically, an amount obeys a power law if it is obtained by a probability distribution according to the $p(k) \propto k^{-\alpha}$ equation, where the exponent is a constant α – scalar parameter of the probabilistic distribution. The scalar parameter typically is in the $2 < \alpha < 3$ range. There may be exceptions. However, according to Ghoshal, Chi & Barabási (2013) α greater than 3 indicates an exponential behavior that is associated with a homogeneous distribution of degree centralities. A homogeneity distribution denotes a quality of the relational structure where there are no hubs or high centrality nodes. In the real world, the scalar parameter α in the range $2 < \alpha < 3$ is combined to $\alpha > 3$, as there is not a single network growth regime. In this sense, an exponential body is coupled to tails that fit the power model $p(k) \propto k^{-\alpha}$.

To characterize a series of empirical observations, the model proposed by the authors is $\hat{\alpha} \cong 1 + n \left[\sum_{i=1}^v \ln \frac{k_i}{k_{min}^{-1/2}} \right]^{-1}$, where k_{min} is considered when there is some limit from which empirical data behave according to the power law. For, as already mentioned, growth regimes overlap. Thus, it is necessary to use a lower limit to restrict the observed data to the region of the phenomenon. And finally, k_i which in this model is a discrete measure – the centrality of degree.

The procedure adopted for each year is, according to Closet, Shalizi & Newman (2009):

1. Estimate parameters k_{min} and $\hat{\alpha}$ of the model.
2. Calculate the goodness-of-fit of the power law, and if the resulting p-value is greater than 0.1, the power law is a plausible hypothesis for the data, otherwise, it is rejected.
3. Compare the power law with alternative hypotheses through a probability ratio test. For each alternative, if the calculated probability ratio is significantly nonzero, then this indicates whether the alternative is favored over the power law model. In this study, we will adopt the comparison with an exponential distribution. Thus, it will be possible to characterize the growth of the network between homogeneity and/or preferential attachment when it occurs and analyze transitions between distinct distributions.

2.5 CAPES and MEC Ordinances

The publication of the ordinances offers a historical series of deliberations that can support the understanding of the results observed in the networks. Some ordinances were selected in which it is believed that they have been/had influence on/in the process of establishing networks among PPGs – see **Erro! Autoreferência de indicador não válida.** in chronological order.

Table 1

Clippings of CAPES and MEC ordinances

Ordinance	Clipping
n° 2.264 19/Dec/1997	Which confers national validity to the titles of Master and Doctor.

Ordinance	Clipping
n° 068 03/Aug/2004	It defines the categories of teachers of the programs of this level of education, and that each evaluation area analyze under which permanent teaching conditions can be linked to itself or to another institution.
n° 5.800 8/Jun/2006	Decree on the Open University System of Brazil - UAB, focused on the development of the modality of distance education.
n°17 28/Dec/2009	It has a master's degree in capes. Training of professional masters qualified to develop activities and technical-scientific work on topics of public interest
n° 3 7/Jan/2010	Which determines that the professor who remains performing his own activities of permanent teacher with the graduate programs of his home institution and to which he was linked at the time of his retirement.
n° 81 3/Jun/2016	Multiple permanent teacher affiliation in up to three (3) PPG's. The workload is established together with the respective Coordinators of the PPG's.
n° 389 23/Mar/2017	It institutes, within the scope of stricto sensu graduate studies, the modalities of master's and professional doctorate. The novelty is for the modality of doctorate, until then not existing in the National Graduate System. The professional master's degree began in the 1990s.
n° 90 24/Apr/2019	It provides about stricto sensu graduate programs in the modality of distance education.

Source: CAPES Portal.

3 METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURE

A problem that has been gaining attention in network science is the genesis of networks (Ferreira, 2004; Guigourès, Boullé & Rossi, 2015; Li et al., 2017). The temporal approach of networks is divided into three forms, (i) the evolution of networks centered on ties, or in how relationships are established or undone, (ii) evolution centered on the vertex, where the objective is to understand how the proximity of a vertex privilege the formation or dissolution of relationships, and (iii) the evolution centered on the digraph (Nicosia, et al., 2012; Casteigts, Flocchini, Quattrociocchi, & Santoro, 2013). The evolution of a digraph D is sequentially delimited by characteristic dates, defined by S_T as $D = Sort(\cup \{S_T(e): e \in E\})$, where S_T is the temporal sequence of a digraph D , $S_T(e)$ is the photo of a network in time and existing at that moment t , and E is the period. The photo corresponds to a chronological order where topological events of the system occur. The idea is simple, transformations can be identified from structural metrics from one static digraph to another in time. Therefore, systemic evolution can be described as a chronological sequence of static digraphs, and descriptive metrics can be extracted and organized on a longitudinal journey. Structural changes can be identified through persistent homologies over time. We will use this technique to detect potentially important structural changes over time.

Persistent homology quantifies individual topological characteristics (events) in the graph according to their significance (or persistence). The set of all features, encoded by the persistence diagram, can be seen as a fingerprint for the graph. Using this fingerprint, the most topologically important structures of subsequent graphs can be robustly compared to small data disturbances (Hajij, Wang, Scheidegger & Rosen, 2018; p. 125).

The adoption of a method such as the temporal approach of networks completes the analytical framework to empirically approach the theory of coevolution of social networks because it inserts in the analytical context the evolutionary aspect. In this article, we will not see the evolutions centered on the vertex and/or ties, although the data set allows such analysis. At an opportune time, one or both approaches will be considered in depth.

3.1 Data collection and analysis

The raw data for the manufacture of the networks were collected from the web page called CAPES Open Data in the Evaluation section of the Stricto Sensu Graduate Program. In this section, excel archives about Professors of the Stricto Sensu Graduate Program in Brazil were collected. These files list the affiliation of teachers' names to PPGs, also qualifying PPGs geographically, legally, and modality (academic or professional), and qualifying teachers as

permanent, collaborator, and visitor. We also collected the Archives of Students of the Stricto Sensu Graduate Program in Brazil, from which the student body of each PPG was totaled – $CorpoDocente_t$. For access to the age of NDP_t , the year of its constitution was collected in the archives Stricto Sensu Graduate Courses of Brazil – PPG_{Idade_t} . For each modality of PPG, it was organized in the Academic and then Professional order. The digraph of each year was elaborated from the path ordered from the criterion $D = (V, A, l, u, c)$ (Bang-Jensen & Gutin, 2007), where the capacity u :

$$\begin{cases} \text{If } CorpoDocente_t = 0 \text{ or } NDP_t = 0 \text{ then } u_t = 0, \text{ otherwise:} \\ u_t = \left(\left(\frac{NDP_t}{CorpoDocente_t} \right) + PPG_{Idade_t} \right) \times CAPES_Note_t \end{cases}$$

Figure 2 - Criterion for determining the capacity of each PPG for each year of analysis – u_t

Source: Prepared by the authors.

The capacity u_t of each modality of PPG was organized in descending order for each year to represent the preferred path for each teacher. The digraph D is formed by the sum of all parallel tracks to abstract the complexity of parallel tracks in the cost c of tie. The cost c of the tie was considered only to represent the thickness of the tie in Figure 10 and Figure 11. For the calculation of metrics and distribution of centralities k_i the digraphs were dichotomized – $to\ c > 0, c = 1, otherwise\ c = 0$.

The results will be organized by year in graphic form and in tables to identify homologous reproductions in time which will allow us to identify changes. The changes identified in time as persistent homologies (Hajij, Wang, Scheidegger & Rosen, 2018) will guide the research of regulatory acts to access the system's constitutive relationships in regulatory domains (Padgett & Powell, 2012, p. 5-7).

4 RESULTS

Throughout its recent history, the Brazilian academy in management has gradually become cohesive among its teaching centers. By 2020, about 1/3 of the number of professor-researchers work simultaneously in about 2.1 graduate programs (PPGs). As we will see later, most multiple affiliations occur within the limits of the Higher Education Institutions - HEI. The data so far do not indicate the possibility of evaluating whether such sharing contributes positively or negatively to the productivity and quality of the whole. What the empirical model indicates is that there is the formation of various systems of learning and feedback, within the limits of the HEIs, and gradually advancing towards transcending the limits of the HEIs. All indications are that the 2000s were marked by most contractual transitions of professors between HEIs and a few cases of professors who over the years participated in more than one PPG, including in different federative units – e.g., Positivo University and PUC in Paraná, and FGV in São Paulo. Near the end of the 2000s and early 2010s, with the multiplication of PPGs in many HEIs, it is beginning to become difficult to identify in the data the cases of contractual transition, and there is a predominance of multiple persistent affiliations – year over year with the same teacher sharing activities in different PPGs and HEIs.

Even though it is a phenomenon that gains traction in the areas of management only since 2004, it is something that has occurred for a long time in other areas of knowledge. CAPES describes in its Newsletter Vol. 5 no. 1 of 1997, the occurrence of PPGs in partnership, consortium, or network in the areas of environmental management and nursing, after noting in field research, and surprisingly as the text reports, that before 1997 there were already stricto sensu programs organized spontaneously in the form of networks to overcome regional limitations of qualified personnel.

4.1 Historical series of nodal and relational metrics

The co-participation of teachers in more than one PPG has occurred since 1990. In Figure 3, the $k_{médio} > 0$ of each year is the indicator of this occurrence. Figure 3 can also be seen that from 2009, there was already a tendency for the ties to overcome the vertices

in quantity. According to Padgett and Powell's coevolutionary theory of social networks (2012), the emergence of a connected neighborhood makes it possible to form cycles among the connected vertices, so the greater the residue of the $k_{\text{médio}}$ the more likely the vertices are connected to create learning circuits – or Hamiltonian cycles. The transition of the residue from a negative value to a positive value indicates that the relational environment starts to have a high probability of multiple learning circuits among PPGs, since from 2013 50% of PPGs start to make up a network component, and in subsequent years such network component continues to grow until it is composed by more than 70% of PPGs in 2020.

Figure 3 - Historical series of the residue $k_{\text{residue}} = k_{\text{médio}} - 1$

Source: Prepared by the authors via UCINET (Borgatti, Everett and Freeman, 2014).

The relational environment is formed by HEIs, which are receptacles of PPGs. Figure 4 that in 1990 about 60% of the HEIs contained at least 1 PPG. In that year the system was formed by less than 50 PPGs. Already in 2020, in addition to significant growth in the number of PPGs, 60% of the HEIs contain 2 or more PPGs as shown by stratification. Remember that we are dealing here with photo that include the areas of Administration and Engineering III. Of course, the HEIs have much more PPGs if we count other areas of knowledge.

Figure 4 - Historical Series Relation HEIs x PPGs

Source: Prepared by the authors

About 97% of the shares occur within the HEIs, and about 3% transcend the limits of institutions and create inter-HEIs relationships. Figure Figure 5 the historical series from 2004 to 2020. In inter-HEIs relations there are cases of contractual transition of teachers, these relationships, even if producing a temporary relationship – 1-year photograph, represents a link. Probably these transition relations are the majority until the year 2010, from then on, the interinstitutional relationship, even if informal, becomes a predominant proportion as we will see later.

Figure 5 - Historical series of institutional and interinstitutional relations

Source: Prepared by the authors.

To characterize another important essence of this system, it is a system where vertices, in addition to relationships, are born and die. To demonstrate this characteristic Figure Figure 6 that the net difference between inflows and outflows is positive and increases from 1990 to 2016, and between 2017 and 2020 the system enters a deceleration regime, grows less in the years 2017 and 2019, and shrinks in the years 2018 and 2020. Finally, they are empirical data, and as such, the system incorporates inflows and outflows of ties and vertices, in the way they occurred.

Figure 6 - Historical series of the difference between inflows and outflows of PPGs to the system

Source: Prepared by the authors.

4.2 Formation of strongly connected components

What the in-depth search shows us is that since 2004, although the networks in previous years have already demonstrated some medium degree – k_{mean} , only from 2004 begin to emerge cycles, and therefore occur the formation of SCCs. There was already something latent in favor of multiple affiliations, regulatory act no. 068 of 03/Aug/2004 only opened the door to the field learning process. Figure Figure 7 us the evolution of the rate of SCCs, and to be more explanatory the figure shows in a combined way the evolution of the number of SCCs and the number of vertices, so it is possible to verify that from 1990 to 2003 the number of vertices is equal to the number of SCCs, that is, all vertices are isolated SCCs. The system started under the logic of skill verticalization. It is a specific case of digraph theory where, even if there are some directional relationships, these only end or begin at the vertex, there is no cycle composition. Cycles, once they are composed, form feedback systems, so they are treated as learning systems (Bang-Jensen & Gutin, 2007).

Using the cyclic integrality rate moving average feature – CR^* , calculated here every two years, indicates two inflection points, one occurred in 2011 and the other occurred in 2016. With this, it is possible to analyze, in a simple way, adjusting a linear function at each pre and post-inflection period. From this analysis it can be inferred that the interlacing activity of PPGs from 2004 to 2010 was further developed with a low diffusion of the area since the $R^2 = 0.6791$ indicates a low adjustment rate. When we applied the same analysis format for the period 2011 to 2015, the linear function adjustment became $R^2 = 0.9393$. Probably the area constituted consensus on the composition of PPGs by multiple affiliations. Returning to the published ordinances we have the ordinances of 2009 – which regulate the professional master's degree and 2010 – that regularize the framework of retirees for the maintenance as permanent teaching.

Figure 7 - SCC rate per year

Source: Prepared by the authors via UCINET (Borgatti, Everett and Freeman, 2014).

In the period from 2011 to 2016, when computing the number of participations with exclusive dedication and dyad per framework among all assets, including assets in the retirement, the professor in retirement phase played a small role in the process of multiple affiliations, in the order of a few tens only – from 10 to 45 occurrences in this period. The vast majority, in the order of hundreds of dyads – from 350 to 700, occur among assets outside the retirement phase. The probable objective of the area when it expressed concern and was met by CAPES via regulatory act no. 3 of Jan 7, 2010, must have been the maintenance of the stability of the system.

Figure 8 - Stratification of relationships by active/active retired framework

Source: Prepared by the authors

The third and final inflection point occurs in 2016, when CAPES regulates the affiliation of permanent teachers in multiple PPGs via regulatory act no. 81 of June 3, 2016, establishing the probability of multiple affiliations to $\frac{1}{3}$, that is, a new neighborhood rule at the maximum limit of affiliations to 3 PPGs. With the responsibility of the program coordinators for the definition of workload. Such regulation produces a brake on the process, this can be noticed when comparing the angular coefficients of the functions – dy/dx first derivative is the velocity constant in this case. The process evolves slower in the period 2016 to 2020 compared to previous periods – dy/dx is equal to 0.0154 for 2004-2010, 0.0219 for 2011-2015, and 0.0135 for 2016-2020. We can consider that there was a learning phase of 2004-2010, a period of high consensus on how to do ($R^2 = 0.9393$) in the period 2011-2015. And then CAPES Ordinance Act 81 inserted the brake.

The simple counting of SCCs and calculation of CR* cyclical integrality in a system designed to represent the emergence of organizational innovations was sensitive to the intertwining of actions among the actors of the system – PPGs and CAPES. This is because the relational space was constituted according to the constitutive criteria of Padgett and Powell (2012) coevolutionary theory of social networks.

4.3 Power law in the trajectory of PPGs

An important feature to be highlighted here is the nature of the system's growth. To this end, it is necessary to explain how PPGs are organized in their minimum unit, so, the operational management of a PPG is collegiate. The way a PPG is constituted is a choice guided by the interests of a collective called collegiate, which is formed predominantly by the permanent teaching nucleus – Teaching Core– within its rules and statutes. Therefore, the choice of affiliation is not part of the interest of new proponents of professor-researcher. It is important to make this distinction because the theory of preferential attachment of Barabási and

Albert (1999), needs to be adjusted to this context. The preferentiality model considers that new vertices tend to bind in larger vertices, often older, but here the preferentiality, when it occurs, is part of the criteria of this collegiate. It is also worth mentioning that the authors' theory of scale transition is a very particular case of networks where there is only the addition of vertices and loops. This is not the case here, in addition to the inflows and outflows of PPGs, the system also incurs inclusions and exclusions of loops. Therefore, we should not expect the power law to present an $\hat{\alpha} = 3$. But we can expect the network to have a power with $\hat{\alpha} > 3$. To characterize whether the probabilistic distribution is characterized by an exponential and/or power distribution, we must perform analyses of the power law by both methods of probabilistic analysis.

Figure 9 – Calculation of $\hat{\alpha}$, p-value for power law and exponential test.

Source: Prepared by the authors via R-Studio and poweRlaw package (Gillespie, 2015) – 8Table 2:Table 2 - Annex.

Figure 9 that the relational trajectory of PPGs has two moments, the first goes from 1998 to 2010 and the second goes from 2011 to 2020. In the first, we see that the condition of preferentiality in affiliation is probably more associated with the transition of teachers among PPGs of different HEIs. First in the years 1998, 1999 and 2000, and then in the years 2005 and 2008. In those years the p-value indicates a power law distribution adjustment. However, the predominance is that PPGs connect according to a logic of homogenization of relationships and, therefore, in an exponential distribution of k_i . This can be seen in the p-value analysis when the chosen model is exponential, unless in the years 2002, 2004 and 2006, from 1998 to 2010 the most adherent probabilistic distribution is exponential. As previously stated, the exponential distribution does not imply preferentiality of connections and, therefore, there is no formation of high centrality PPGs – see Figure 10. The year 2010 was chosen to represent the logic of the homogenization of relationships according to a probabilistic distribution of k_i exponential.

Figure 11 - 2020 graph of the year with PPGs grouped by HEI

Note: Vertices in green - PPGs Profess., in blue - PPGs Acad., Box - HEI, black trace - intra HEI ties and orange trace - inter HEIs loops. Source: Prepared by the authors via NodeXL (Smith, 2014).

In 2014 the network operation model is transposed to the stricto sensu of management areas in the form of professional masters. And in this new area inserts a network fold constituting your core teaching in a star network format to functionally adjust to the criteria of the knowledge area of Administration. Padgett and Powell (2012, p. 5-7) propose that the key to the classification of this phenomenon is the process of relational reconfiguration of the system of which this invention is part – and this occurs in the years 2018 to 2020. In this new context, the new PROFIAP and PROFNIT programs cause the change in the K_{mean} of the relational growth structure, producing a tension between the predominant rationale of homogenization, to a rationale of preferential attachment. Not for nothing the CAPES ordinance no. 90 of Apr 24, 2019 was published to regulate distance learning in the stricto sensu. Even if by 2020 no PPG at a distance has been approved for operation in Brazil.

Therefore, we still have questions about how to categorize these programs. In their regiments they are categorized as national networks, they call themselves face-to-face, but contemplate activities at a distance. So, they're hybrid, near-distance, or semi-face-to-face. That is, the way they are categorized does not necessarily solve their bias, which remains scoffed under the promise of a networking and face-to-face operation. But it is perfectly understandable for such an uncertainty, after all this is a time of change, the dust is in the air, and as Powell, Packalen and Whittington (2012) write it is important to highlight where the dust comes from and, most importantly, it must be accepted that the actors of this movement continue to reformulate their actions and to raise or settle this cloud. So, what is being identified is an environment that can become heterogeneous in the way of operationalizing its production process from the contribution of remotization technologies. However, there is still no final configuration.

5 ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The organizational genesis of the system tells us that, from 2004 on, the system began to organize itself into cycles of autocatalysis among teaching cores (Padgett and Powell, 2012). The cycles of autocatalysis denote that the system, among its teaching cores, begins to be inserted into learning cycles. Over the years, the system intensifies the composition in autocatalysis cycles, ranging from 2004 to 2020 from 10% to 25% of the teaching cores in this learning model (Padgett, 1997). Since 2013, the teaching cores are becoming increasingly intertwined, because from this year there is the formation of the main component composed of 50% of the PPGs, by 2020 this component reaches 70% of the PPGs, which favors the dissemination of practices.

In the regulatory dimension, which we are adopting here as a way of access to constitutive relations between the domain of teaching and the regulatory domain, we identified regulatory acts that in 2004 authorize multiple teacher affiliation, in 2009 regulate the professional strictu sensu and in 2010 regulates the maintenance of retired teachers as permanent teachers. Regulatory acts standardize the system and the structure in response, but of course, there were already manifestations and latent plans. This demonstrates the constitutive relationships between different domains for organizational novelties (Padget and Powell, 2012, p. 11). Of course, such regulatory acts are not only aimed at the areas of Administration and Engineering III, but it is also for all areas of knowledge, so it is to be assumed that this is a transposition between multiple domains of teaching mediated by the regulatory agency and social technologies.

5.1 Homogenization and/or the logic of preferentiality?

The main finding of this study is the logic of preferentiality and homogenization. This is an unfolding of the network among teaching cores. The logic of homogeneous relationships is predominant. The logic of preferential attachment is present in only three PPGs. This is evident from 2016 to 2020. In this period there is the emergence of an organizational novelty, the emergence of a new organizational species represented by three professional PPGs that organize their teaching cores with k_{mean} standing out for being taller than other organizations. There are three PPGs the PROFIAP of ANDIFES, PROFINIT of FORTEC, and Management For Competitiveness of FGV-SP. All these programs are hybrids in the offer of face-to-face teaching and sociotechnical resources for the remotization of education, but the PPGs of ANDIFES and FORTEC have peculiar characteristics, these organizations are national associations of federal HEIs. Speciation can be radical or gradual as stated (Padget and Powell, 2012) these cases represent a radically different form from previously existing models. It is possible that the Management For Competitiveness of FGV-SP is also speciation in the sense that, as PROFIAP and PROFINIT, it contemplates, in addition to a face-to-face approach, socio-technical resources of remotization, but in a process of teacher sharing that is better represented by a logic of homogenization of relationships. Contributing, in addition to an exponential distribution of centralities k_i , but also for a logic of preferentiality in connections, that is, a distribution of the power law. These three PPGs interfere to such a point in the probabilistic distribution of the centralities that mischaracterize exponential distribution – in the years 2018, 2019, and 2020 the p-value for exponential distribution is $p \leq 0.1$. On the contrary, the system becomes characterized by the power law, with $k_{min} = 3$ for 2018 and 2019, and $k_{min} = 4$ for 2020. Only because a tail adjustment is configured that we can assume that the system is composed of two systemic organization logics. Figure 12 shows how PPGs are organized, the difference is in the cyclic integrality rate– CR^* for each adjacent matrix to the selected PPGs, that, for PROFIAP and PROFNIT, are 0.27 and 0.32 respectively, and 0.73 for the FGV-SP’s PPG. PROFIAP and PROFNIT PPGs are poor in strongly connected components. Being part of a strongly connected structure indicates that PPG is inserted in a relational context oriented to organizational learning (Padget, 1997). On the other hand, organizations rich in strong vertices themselves, such as PROFIAP and PROFNIT, indicate that even with preferential relationships they behave as if they incorporate all the skills and competencies necessary for their operation (Padget, 1997).

Figure 12 - Sub-digraphs of high-central professional PPGs

Source: Prepared by the authors via NodeXL (Smith, 2014) and iGraph package at R-Studio (Csardi, G., & Nepusz, T., 2006).

Even if they are not DL operations, these PPGs incorporate socio-technical capabilities of virtual and remote content. However, in the regulatory domain, the academic community sees in this specification the basis of a model of DL, even if it is not, as elaborated in the previous section, but the community, through its representatives, is reacting to the model of preferentiality, first by ordinance no. 81 of June 3, 2016, which restricts teacher sharing to 1/3 PPGs, and later in ordinance No. 90 of Apr 24, 2019, which imposes narrow criteria for the authorization of capes strictu sensu DL. CAPES, until 2020, had not authorized any proposals. But it cannot be failed to note that the very existence of this ordinance is also a sign that the community understands that the contribution of new social technologies of remotization of teaching in the strictu sensu is an inevitable path and, therefore, the theme is in frank debate. It will be necessary to keep up.

It is worth mentioning that in this study there is no interest in taking any of the flags as the best, although we understand that the remotization of teaching classes is a walk without return, here the interest is the coevolutionary theory of social networks, and how the evolution of networks among teaching cores in the areas of management reveals the constitution of a new relational structure in strictu sensu graduate studies in Brazil. Understand where these organizations are coming from, what are the motivations of regulatory acts, and why these tensions understand the opposing forces. From the coevolutionary theory of social networks (Padgett and Powell, 2012, p.11-26), currently, we are identifying transpositions among adjacent domains. It was not clear where the logic of teacher sharing is coming from, it is a solution already present in some knowledge areas since the 1990s. The logic of preferential attachment (Barabási and Albert, 1999) seem to be coming from the UAB model.

For now, and to elaborate reading of the system, it may be possible to draw a parallel between homogenization and face-to-face education, and preferentiality in connection with semi-face-to-face or distance learning. Thus, we can say that the logic of preferentiality is correlated with technological advances in the virtualization and remotization of the classroom, promoting the uncoupling of the physical limitations of face-to-face teaching, that is, the ecosystem of strictu sensu in management is initiating the process of functional review by transposition and, mainly, by the refunctionality of a DL model for the strictu sensu context in management – see Padgett and Powell (2012, Pag. 1-29 and 168-207), and the areas are holding a wide-ranging debate on the subject. So, it's understandable to have tension among the models, it's something not invented by the traditional graduate community in management. And there are other interests in the field of action, the community is not only formed by public and non-profit organizations but there is also private initiative. But it is possible to infer so far that the evolutionary factor of teaching networks in strictu sensu management in Brazil are social technologies. Distance learning is an operational modality. For, if in the 1990s network operations existed to overcome limitations of qualified personnel, in 2020 perhaps the tension between the market and public budget is the most central motivation. Further investigations will be needed.

6 CONCLUSION

How does the evolution of networks among teaching cores in the areas of management, and regulatory acts, reveal the constitution of organizational novelties in strictu sensu programs in Brazil?

The question is about how the evolution of networks between teaching cores contributes to the emergence of distance learning in the context of strictu sensu graduate studies in the areas of Brazilian management. So, the trajectory of the system shows us that teacher sharing has existed in academia since the 1990s, and regulatory acts have boosted the system, giving validity to logic. However, we never considered the possibility of transposition of the DL model into the context of graduate studies in administration. The UAB was instituted by decree of the MEC in 2006. At the time of its constitution, the UAB should give need training of teachers

and managers for basic education. However, now, his function has been redesigned to provide professional training for managers in public administration (PROFIAP) and innovation (PROFNIT). A refunctionality process where the main actors of the preferred attachment model are ANDIFES and FORTEC – both federal HEI associations, together with MEC and CAPES. While the actors of the predominant homogeneous connection model are PPGs, area representatives, evaluation system, and CAPES. Two distinct forms of action, one centered on the design of a new socio-technical system of strictu sensu, and the other on the quality of its results and productivity of its contingent.

It is evident that reality, like that conceived by the area, is part of a reference that is being challenged. Frontier actors are playing their part in proposing the transposition of the limits imposed by ontological assumptions of the areas. And this may be explained by the exercise of the centrality of intermediation. From where comes the need to expand the study to other domains and identify other constitutive relationships.

7 BIBLIOGRAFIA

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8 ANNEX - PROBABILISTIC ADJUSTMENT TABLES TO THE k_{in-out}

Table 2:

Adjust power distribution and exponential

Year	N	N connect	Power						Exponential					
			k_{min}	C	$\hat{\alpha}$	GoF $p < 0.1$	Tail	$p \leq 0.1$	k_{min}	C	$\hat{\gamma}$	GoF $p < 0.1$	Tail	$p \leq 0.1$
1998	65	27	1	24.5	2.59	0.04	26	0.55	1	23.7	1.15	0.05	26	0.32
1999	83	42	2	16.1	4.01	0.08	19	0.28	2	15.1	1.31	0.05	19	0.41
2000	97	51	2	20.7	3.96	0.09	24	0.15	2	19.3	1.30	0.06	24	0.25
2001	99	56	1	74.0	2.21	0.14	56	0.00	1	65.2	0.88	0.05	56	0.21
2002	107	69	2	37.5	3.41	0.13	34	0.01	1	83.5	0.83	0.06	69	0.06
2003	114	85	1	117.2	2.17	0.13	85	0.00	1	104.3	0.82	0.04	85	0.22
2004	129	89	1	120.2	2.19	0.13	89	0.00	1	106.6	0.85	0.06	89	0.02
2005	145	104	2	56.6	3.56	0.05	55	0.15	2	54.1	1.06	0.04	55	0.18
2006	159	110	2	48.6	3.65	0.10	49	0.00	1	122.2	0.93	0.05	110	0.03
2007	177	134	2	73.4	3.42	0.07	67	0.01	2	69.7	1.00	0.02	67	0.67
2008	183	140	3	31.6	4.74	0.06	32	0.25	1	176.3	0.79	0.03	140	0.19
2009	193	145	3	60.4	3.90	0.08	47	0.05	2	121.3	0.71	0.04	89	0.30
2010	201	158	2	120.0	3.17	0.06	97	0.02	2	116.1	0.85	0.02	97	0.78
2011	220	166	5	6.2	7.53	0.05	7	0.47	3	49.1	0.97	0.01	46	0.91
2012	228	179	4	16.0	8.46	0.01	28	0.92	4	15.8	1.73	0.01	28	0.99
2013	248	191	5	7.0	8.91	0.04	10	0.66	2	155.4	0.88	0.03	134	0.36
2014	267	227	4	34.5	6.09	0.05	37	0.31	4	33.6	1.16	0.04	37	0.28
2015	288	243	4	38.9	5.55	0.05	37	0.27	2	206.4	0.77	0.03	161	0.23
2016	309	263	4	67.3	4.35	0.04	48	0.55	2	251.2	0.65	0.02	173	0.52
2017	316	263	4	79.4	4.10	0.03	53	0.84	2	179.0	0.61	0.02	179	0.82
2018	313	269	3	150.0	3.56	0.03	104	0.41	2	285.0	0.59	0.05	184	0.01
2019	326	291	3	198.5	3.31	0.07	126	0.01	2	337.4	0.51	0.05	201	0.01
2020	317	283	4	97.0	4.11	0.05	65	0.26	2	311.2	0.55	0.04	193	0.02

Source: Prepared by the authors via R-Studio and powerLaw package (Gillespie, 2015).

Figure 13 - Years 1998-2020 - Power adjustment (red) and exponential (green)
 Source: Produced by the authors